

ISSUES ON THE IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON THE INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *The article covers the content of improving the system of preparing future teachers for educational activities on the basis of an analysis of the literature on Innovation, describes the main task of the system of preparing future teachers for educational activities, its components. Also, in the organization of the preparation of future teachers for educational activities, the prerequisites for ensuring an innovative approach were classified and appropriate recommendations and conclusions were developed.*

Keywords: *science, science, system, innovation, approach, process, improvement, education, standard, activity, innovation, result, innovation activity.*

In our country, special importance is attached to the issue of creating a holistic system for introducing innovations related to the preparation of future teachers for educational activities, training pedagogical personnel who are eager for innovation, who can engage in innovative activities. One of the obvious actions towards the effective organization of competitive modern personnel training work on the basis of high technologies is the law “on innovative activities” adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 7, 2020 [1].

One of the tasks of organizing educational activities in higher educational institutions is to ensure the effectiveness of measures aimed at preparing future teachers for educational activities, for the effective implementation of which it is necessary to develop, improve existing directions.

After all, the preparation of future teachers for educational activities on the basis of innovative approaches forms an integral part of the educational and educational process. The ideas of upbringing instilled in him, the acquisition of moral norms occur flawlessly, based on generally accepted rules.

An important place in education is occupied by the improvement of the educational process without certain methods, tools, instructions for pedagogical innovation. In this process, modernized technologies in connection with new requirements are considered innovation.

The organization of innovative activities in higher educational institutions is the opportunities, activities and productive results of professors and teachers aimed at raising the educational process to a quality level, applying innovations to the educational and educational system.

Determining the essence of the preparation of future teachers for educational activities on the basis of innovative approaches, raising it to a new level in terms of content and quality, noting that the term “innovation” was originally coined at the beginning of the 20th century by the Austrian economist Y.Used by Schumpeter in the field of Economics [2].

There are different approaches to such concepts as” innovation“,” innovative approach“,” innovative activity“. In fact, the concept of” innovation “is derived from the Latin word” novatio“, and the suffix” innovation, update “(or” change“),” in “is translated from Latin as” in the

direction“, if this is translated in the form of a holistic” innovatio “ – interpreted as” in the direction of change”.

The concept of innovation is described in the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan “as follows:” innovation is derived from the English word” innovationas”, which means such a meaning as invention, introduced innovation - funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of generations of technology and technology; - innovations in such areas as technology, technology, labor organization and management, based on advanced experience and scientific and technological achievements, as well as their application

N.Muslimov promotes the idea that innovation brings innovation into the process, G.M.Kodjaspirova, A.Yu.Kodjaspirovs have stated that the words innovation are synonymous with each other, meaning “innovation, new procedures, ” M.M.Patashnik, A.G.The Homeric, on the other hand, considered the words” new innovation“,” innovation is the introduction of innovation ” to be synonymous. In fact, innovation is – it is precisely the novelty of the tool, method, method and method, while innovation means the transition of the system from one state to another based on the introduction of innovations into the process, its components, the environment.

It is possible to say that”innovation “is not an introduction into the process of the concepts of” new“,” innovation ” in content, but a literal innovation only if this or that innovation provides a high effect of the expected result and is an object of large-scale need.

N.Mamadov and summarizing his research on the same problem, he argues that innovation is the result of innovation in certain areas that serve a high level of socio-economic, scientific and technical efficiency, along with the transformation of the management object. N.Mamadov was able to see only the socio-economic, scientific and technical aspects of innovation, in fact, innovation is a factor in obtaining a high level of result even in the educational process.

Based on the analysis of literature on innovation, on the basis of an innovative approach, the main task of the system of preparing future teachers for educational activities is the development of a culture of organizing educational activities in future teachers (the formation of adequate ideas about the purpose, content, essence of educational activity and their interdependence, conducting substantive reflections on the organization;

Social adaptation of the builders of the new Uzbekistan to the startegic changes taking place in our country and the selection of the right path in it, the formation of decision-making skills, while increasing their knowledge of the necessary basic competencies that will be needed in the future for them; the formation of practical skills in them to make the right choice in

The processes of creation, development, improvement, popularization, implementation of innovations can be called the main components of innovative activity. As a result of the use of innovations in educational and educational processes, such skills as critical thinking, independent thinking, acceptance of independent conclusions, Free statement of one's own opinion, adherence to democratic principles are formed in future teachers.

In order to ensure an innovative approach to organizing the preparation of future teachers for educational activities, it is advisable to adhere to several of the following conditions:

- coverage of all future teachers in preparation for educational activities;
- taking into account the spiritual preparation of future teachers for the organization in the preparation for educational activities;
- work future teachers in groups and improve productivity;

- clear determination of time in preparation for educational activities.

In preparing future teachers for educational activities, the teacher is required to have a highly developed ability to think, erudition, the ability to observe deeply and the ability to solve problematic situations.

On the basis of an innovative approach, the following can be attributed to the main tasks of innovative technologies in the preparation work for educational activities:

- general, holistic development of the preparation process for educational activities;
- determination of specific goals and objectives that should be solved in the process of preparation for educational activities;
- development of the content of the preparation process for educational activities;
- creation of conditions for free, independent activities of future teachers in the process of preparation for educational activities;
- control and evaluation of the activities of future teachers.

The analysis of our scientific research carried out during our pedagogical activity in higher educational institutions showed that along with the positive pedagogical experience observed in higher education, there are some reasons that minimize the possibility of active involvement of an innovative approach. These are:

- in the process of providing knowledge in pedagogical disciplines, one should not systematically rely on non-teaching methods;
- ignoring cognitive, motivational, technological, praxological, organizational components in the education of Pedagogical Sciences;

Lack of knowledge of cognitive, emotional-figurative, motivational criteria for preparing future teachers of teachers of higher educational institutions for educational activities;

The absence of the necessary base on the organizational, developmental, practical, reflex, analytical stages of the organization of educational activities of future teachers in higher educational institutions.

Hence, an innovative approach serves to organize the educational process on a scientific basis in the preparation of future teachers for educational activities, as well as to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process of a creative approach in relationships.

Innovation in the field of upbringing is systems or long – term initiatives based on the socialization of children and adolescents and the use of new educational tools that help reduce asocial phenomena in the youth environment.

Innovative activity is not only the ability to solve a certain range of problems as a system of action among social entities, which is considered the most important part of theory and practice, and is aimed at further improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object, but also to have motivational training to solve problems in any situation.

Based on the analysis of the literature, the research carried out, we came to the conclusion that an innovative approach in the preparation of future teachers for educational activities is updated in accordance with modern norms and requirements, technical guidelines, quality indicators in the organization of educational activities. It can be said that nowadays, without innovative ideas in the world, without the achievements of science, it will be difficult for any industry to develop.

When introducing innovations into educational activity, it was determined that it belongs to all components of educational processes: content, purpose, tools, methods and results.

On the basis of an innovative approach, the development and implementation of the process of forming the preparation of future teachers for educational activities requires:

- scientific and practical approach to the process of formation of readiness of future teachers for educational activities;
- to draw the attention of future teachers to the issues of using the methods, methods and forms of the process of preparing for educational activities;
- creation of a system for the formation of readiness of future teachers for educational activities on the basis of an innovative approach;
- development of mechanisms for their stimulation in order to activate the process of improving the readiness of future teachers for educational activities on the basis of an innovative approach;
- to attract future teachers to more innovative activities;
- development and introduction into practice methods of improving the readiness of future teachers for educational activities;
- development of prospective tasks of improving the readiness of future teachers for educational activities;
- to identify the components of improving the readiness of future teachers for educational activities [5].

Hence, the following can be attributed to the components of the preparation of future teachers for educational activities:

- pedagogical, psychological knowledge;
- pedagogical skills;
- educational qualities;
- educational knowledge, personal characteristics that allow you to master skills.

In order for future teachers to successfully carry out educational activities, they themselves are required to be competent in this area.

This requirement requires a new approach to the purpose and content of the implementation of innovative technologies in practical activities to prepare future educators for educational activities.

First of all, in the process of building a new Uzbekistan, it is necessary to restore our great spirituality, to establish a healthy lifestyle in the minds of all citizens, first of all, youth as one of the top priorities in the politics of our country, to harmoniously prepare future teachers preparing for pedagogical activity at the stage of higher education of the;

Secondly, there is a social necessity for the education of such important human qualities as respect for the motherland, loyalty, willpower, entrepreneurship, kindness, patience, perseverance, conscious discipline, national pride, pride, respect for the ancestral norm, fear not of difficulties, loyalty to the motherland, respect for others, willpower from an early age;

Thirdly, the work on the restoration of our national spirituality and the radical reform of folk education strengthen the tendency of great attention to the upbringing of a harmonious, healthy generation in all respects in our society;

Fourth, the social necessity of preparing future teachers for educational activities on the basis of innovative approaches.

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